

Lightweight Sandboxing for Cloud-native 6G Services and Applications

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Overview

- Demo 1: Application execution modes using a simple Knative Serverless function
- Demo 2: vAccel: Hardware-acceleration abstraction using ML models, running on various configurations & modes using the same binary application (OCI artifact).
- Demo 3: Build process Pipeline (multiple architectures, multiple modes of execution).

Introduction - About the Team

- Research in virtualization systems
- Involved in Research & Commercial projects
- Focus on systems software
 - Homogenize application deployment in heterogeneous infrastructure
 - Optimize application execution
 - Bring cloud-native concepts to Edge / Far-Edge devices

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Introduction - Kata-containers Overview

Kata Containers is an open-source project designed to provide the benefits of both containers and virtual machines (VMs) for workload isolation and security.

Key points:

- Combines the speed of containers with the security of VMs.
- Ideal for multi-tenant environments, edge computing, and highly regulated industries.
- Compatible with various high-level runtimes & orchestrators

Introduction - High-level Architecture

Traditional Containers

Kata Containers

Introduction - Advantages and Applications

- Enhanced Security: Isolation provided by VM-level separation improves security posture.
- Performance: Lightweight architecture minimizes overhead compared to traditional VMs.
- Use Cases:
 - Secure Multi-Tenancy: Ideal for cloud providers hosting multiple customers' workloads.
 - Edge Computing: Ensures security and isolation in edge environments.
 - Compliance: Meets stringent security and compliance requirements in industries like finance and healthcare.

Introduction - Container runtimes integration

runtime vs runtime-rs

runtime vs runtime-rs

runtime-rs - hypervisor support

Hypervisor	runtime	runtime-rs
QEMU	★	☆
Cloud-hypervisor	★	☆
Firecracker	★	☆
Dragonball	—	★

Use-cases

Serverless Sandboxes

Expose hardware
acceleration functions

Use-cases

Sandbox user-submitted code:

- Protect the infrastructure from malicious users
- Extend Knative's threat model

API-remoting for sandboxed workloads:

- User-code never touches the accelerator
- Accelerator sharing without PCI/mediated passthrough

Lightweight sandboxes for Serverless Functions

- deploy httpreply service
- simple HTTP header echo

Point to:

- <https://hellocontainer.camad.nbfc.io>
- <https://hellors.camad.nbfc.io/>
- <https://helloclh.camad.nbfc.io/>
- <https://helloqemu.camad.nbfc.io/>
- <https://hellofc.camad.nbfc.io/>

urunc: the unikernel container runtime!

- CRI-compatible runtime written in Go
- Treats unikernels as processes -- directly manages applications
- Spawn unikernel VMs with generic hypervisors
- Extensible, easy to add support for more unikernel frameworks & hypervisors
- Hides complexity of unikernel framework-specific hypervisor and command line options

Isolation
Boundaries

Lightweight sandboxes for Serverless Functions

- deploy httpreply service
- simple HTTP header echo

Point to:

- <https://hellouruncfc.camad.nbfc.io>
- <https://hellouruncqemu.camad.nbfc.io/>

Use-cases - Hardware Acceleration

API-remoting for sandboxed workloads:

- User-code never touches the accelerator
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WiP, under development!

<https://docs.vaccel.org/>

 [nubificus/vaccel](https://github.com/nubificus/vaccel)

 vaccel

Use-cases - NEC's SOL

App

NN Model

```
my_model =  
tf.keras.models.load_model('saved_model/my_model')  
...  
my_model.predict(Data)
```

App

NN Model

```
my_model = vaccel.load("ab134-f67134-314dc4")  
...  
my_model.predict_in_network(Data)
```



```
#ifndef __libNN_  
#define __libNN_  
#ifdef __cplusplus  
extern "C" {  
#endif  
    void predict_init(const int deviceId);  
    int predict_seed(const int64_t seed);  
    void predict(void* ctx, const float* L0, float** L47);  
#ifdef  
__cplusplus  
}  
#endif  
#endif
```

Use-cases - NEC's SOL [demo]

Integrate SOL's functionality to vAccel

- Keep API compatibility
 - eg. `sol_predict()`
- Use shared objects, directly from SOL's optimization output
- minimal overhead compared to stock SOL case
- Demo: alexnet image classification:
 - Stock Torch
 - SOL
 - vAccel SOL

Use-cases - BERT Torch example [demo]

- Simple Torch example:
 - BERT model, speech classification
 - hate-speech
 - offensive-language
 - neutral
 - CPU / GPU implementation
- 1000 tweets
- **Run locally (CPU/GPU)**
- Run in a sandbox container (CPU, no GPU)
- Run in a sandbox container (GPU, vAccel)

Host Kernel

Host Kernel

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vaccel

Use-cases - TVM example [demo]

- Simple image classify example:
 - RESNET models, image classification
 - 18, 34, 50, 101, 102
 - CPU
- random input data
- Run locally (CPU, Torch)
- Run locally (CPU, TVM)
- Run in a sandbox container (CPU, TVM)

Application Build Pipeline

Application Build Pipeline

← OCI image push

✓ Add generic build manifest #91

Re-run all jobs

🕒 Latest #7

Summary

Jobs

- ✓ prepare
- ✓ build (x86_64, httprepy, qemu) ▾
- ✓ build (x86_64, httprepy, fc) ▾
- ✓ build (aarch64, httprepy, qemu) ▾
- ✓ build (aarch64, httprepy, fc) ▾
- ✓ buildgeneric (x86_64, httprepy-... ▾
- ✓ buildgeneric (aarch64, httprepy... ▾
- ✓ manifest (httprepy, qemu) ▾
- ✓ manifest (httprepy, fc) ▾
- ✓ manifestgeneric (httprepy, go) ▾

Run details

- 🕒 Usage
- 📄 Workflow file

Re-run triggered 4 hours ago	Status	Total duration	Artifacts
ananos #2 feat_unify	Success	4m 43s	-

oci.yml

on: pull_request

DESIRE6G

Part of the work presented is supported by Horizon Europe RIA action,
DESIRE6G (GA: 101096466)

Scan the QR codes and spawn serverless functions!

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Thanks!

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